

DEM generalization using polygonal simplification

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Abstract—Generalization methods and their quality is a very important element of geomorphometric research. Polygonal simplification methods in generalization can generally preserve the basic shapes well even at a higher level of generalization. The limited suitability for subsequent mathematical modeling is a major limitation of the use of TIN-based generalization (polygonal simplification) in geomorphometry. Our main goal was to build a method for generalizing the DEM of the land surface using polygonal simplification and to create a generalized model at any level of generalization suitable for further analysis. This involves converting the resulting coarse TIN to a smooth grid. We have created an algorithm that combines well-known algorithms for individual stages of the generalization process with a new method of anisotropic subdivision that increases the quality of the process. The algorithm consists of three main parts: generalization, skeletonization, and smoothing. The main generalization procedure uses Quadratic Error Metric Simplification (QEMS) on the polyhedral model. A smooth surface is created by Laplacian smoothing and Loop subdivision methods. With a greatly simplified model, the level of smoothing required to mitigate the triangular structure is high and thus has the undesirable effect of smoothing the actual edges. We improved the algorithm by using an additional step between generalization and smoothing. The algorithm creates a detailed triangular skeleton using our new anisotropic subdividing triangles based on QEMS quadrics at the vertices. The result shows that the algorithm can successfully progressively remove small features, but also preserve the basic shapes of the landscape surface. The output mesh is also sufficiently smooth without triangular artifacts from the polyhedral TIN model.

I. INTRODUCTION

With highly detailed and accurate LiDAR DEMs now widely available, the problems of geomorphometric investigation have shifted from data error and sampling adequacy to how the surface is actually defined [1]. Research has demonstrated that neither the data's initial scale, nor the highest resolution, guarantee the best

representation, suggesting that scale optimization is a complex but necessary problem [2]. This confirms that generalization methods and their quality is a very important element of geomorphometric research.

The use of grid-based generalization methods predominates in geomorphometry, although many generalization methods have been developed for TIN-based DEMs [3]. Polygonal simplification methods (a group of TIN-based generalization methods) can generally preserve basic shapes well at a higher degree of generalization [4].

The limited suitability for subsequent mathematical modeling is the main limitation of the use of TIN--based generalization in geomorphometry. Land surface curvatures and other higher order parameters are calculated almost exclusively from grids. Therefore, conversion of the resulting TIN to a smooth grid is necessary. Generalization methods used in landscape modeling skip this phase. Separate conversion methods to create a raster grid from a TIN are not very common. If available, they are very basic using linear or simple interpolation, e.g. TIN To Raster in ArcGIS [5]. This is not suitable for generating a grid from a highly generalized TIN, as triangle artifacts remain visible.

Our main goal was to compose a method to generalize the DEM of the land surface using polygonal simplification and create a generalized model at an arbitrary level of generalization suitable for further analysis. This means that the key is to find a balance between preserving the characteristic shapes of the land surface and smoothing it enough for calculations without triangular artifacts.

The construction of a smooth surface over a triangular mesh is an important topic in geometric modeling, and various techniques have been proposed for this problem [6]. They used either triangular patches or refinement schemes. It has been proven that patches with smooth interpolation schemes often generate extraneous folds [7]. In connection with the properties

of the generalized model, the used polygonal simplification is better complemented with the approximating subdivision surfaces. This combination can be supplemented and refined, and then forms the integrated generalization algorithm that we present below.

II. METHODS

A. Quadric Error Metric Simplification

The *Quadric Error Metric Simplification* (QEMS) method [8] is a well-known method for simplifying a polyhedral surface. It was developed primarily for computer graphics; however, it is universal and suitable for use in land surface modeling too [3]. It uses the edge contraction procedure to simplify the model geometry.

QEMS uses the same metric to calculate the weight of edge contraction and optimal vertex placement. This metric is based on the quadratic distances of the new vertex from the individual planes of the triangles with the original merged vertices. An isosurface of constant distance is a quadric (which gives the method its name) and its parameters are stored in the vertices in the form of a 4x4 matrix. A quadric is an ellipsoid if not degenerate. The resulting quadric after edge collapse is the sum of the quadrics of the merged vertices and therefore preserves information about the shape of the surrounding surface [9]. Visualized quadrics on a simplified model are shown in Fig. 1.

B. Quadric Error Subdivision

To preserve as much shape information as possible from the simplified model from the QEMS method, we created the *Quadric Error Subdivision* (QES) method. It enables the creation of a significantly simplified model by QEMS, but prepares a detailed skeleton for subsequent operations on the polyhedral model (e.g. smoothing). The main idea is to reuse the surface shape information stored in the vertices during QEMS.

Figure 1. Quadric isosurfaces of the simplified model vertices

QES uses a triadic subdivision where each original triangle is replaced by 9 new ones. The basic division uses the PN triangle subdivision presented in [7]. The difference is that the new vertices along the edges are not in the tangent plane of the original vertex (since they are not patch control points and lie on the surface instead) but at a distance of $\frac{2}{3}$ between the tangent plane and the edge of the triangle (Fig. 2).

This is anisotropic subdivision, the new vertices along the edges of the triangle are not evenly spaced but are shifted towards the nearest original vertex based on the shape of the QEMS quadrics at that vertex. The ratio of the shift is equal to the contraction of the quadric from the normalized sphere in the direction from the vertex to the new vertex (Fig. 3). The calculation of the central control point is based on the position of the other new vertices along the edges, so the shift is used without changing the referenced equation. The shape of the created triangles follows the shape of the representing surface.

C. Laplacian smoothing

Laplacian smoothing is a simple, yet effective technique for polyhedral surface smoothing. For each vertex in a mesh, a new position is chosen based on local information (the position of neighbors) and the vertex is moved there. This displacement can

Figure 2. Basic localization of subdivision vertices - modified PN triangle subdivision.

Figure 3. Anisotropic triadic subdivision using the shape of quadric isosurfaces in vertices (2D view). Arrows (a) show a vertex shift (b) dependent on the shape change of the sphere (c) to the quadric (d) direction of the triangle edge (e).

be written as the Laplacian operator $U(P)$ for the point. Local update rule

$$P \leftarrow P + \lambda U(P) \quad (2)$$

applied to each point of a polyhedral surface is called Laplacian surface smoothing. The factor λ is typically a small positive number and the process (2) is performed repeatedly [10]. With more iterations and higher λ , the smoothed surface has a strong degree of shrinkage.

D. Loop subdividing

A subdivision surface algorithms use a recursive refinement scheme to better approximate the underlying curved surface. The Loop method for subdivision surfaces [11] is an approximating subdivision scheme for triangular meshes. It is based on iterative refinement of the triangular mesh using dyadic split operation – each edge of the triangular mesh is split into two, and new vertices are reconnected to form 4 new triangles.

The position of new, but also original vertices, is calculated based on a three-directional quartic box spline. This spline basis function is C^2 -continuous. The Loop scheme produces surfaces that are C^2 -continuous everywhere except at extraordinary vertices (whose valence $N \neq 6$), where they are C^1 -continuous.

III. ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION

A. Overview

The presented algorithm contains procedures for generalizing the DEM of the land surface up to a very high level of generalization and creates a smooth generalized model suitable for further analysis. The algorithm consists of three main parts:

1. Generalization
2. Skeletonization
3. Smoothing

The main generalization procedure uses the QEMS on a polyhedral model as presented in [3]. The input and output of the algorithm is a raster DEM, therefore a data structure conversion is required. However, converting a generalized triangular mesh to a raster grid (calculated from a smooth and curved surface) is a challenge. The smooth surface is created by Laplacian smoothing and Loop subdivision methods. When targeting a highly simplified model, the level of smoothing required to mitigate the triangular structure is high and thus has the undesirable effect of smoothing the actual edges. We improved the algorithm by creating a detailed triangular skeleton using our novel anisotropic subdividing triangles based on QEMS quadrics at the vertices. The result of smoothing after anisotropic subdividing significantly better represents the original land surface.

B. Generalization

The preparatory part for the generalization is the Delaunay triangulation of the points on each non-empty cell of the elevation raster, creating an initial triangular model. This model is generalized by QEMS, the end condition is the final number of triangles. The amount of generalization is the main parameter of the algorithm, written as a fraction of triangles after applying QEMS. A meaningful value is in the tens, or even hundreds for a very high level of generalization. This value also characterizes the level of generalization of the results.

C. Skeletonization

We reuse the quadric parameters stored in each of the vertices. Anisotropic displacement of QES method is based on the transformation of a sphere into an ellipsoidal isosurface. The transformation matrix is calculated from the quadric parameters by Cholesky decomposition [9]. Changing the new position is based on applying a transformation matrix to the edge vector.

D. Smoothing

The amount of smoothing can be tuned by adjusting the number of iterations of the Laplacian smoothing. More iterations are suitable for smoother land surfaces. Before Loop subdivision, we fix the 3-valence triangles that can cause smoothing artifacts. The second iteration of the Loop subdivision is used when a detailed result grid is desired compared to the size of the triangles in the generalized TIN.

IV. RESULTS

As an input for generalization testing, we utilized aerial LiDAR raster DEM products with a resolution of 1 meter, obtained from various regions of Slovakia and different types of land surfaces. Each of the research areas selected for this study, covering several square kilometers, were primarily located in regions where previous geomorphological research had been conducted. The initial grids were generalized to many levels to confirm the applicability of the algorithm in different conditions. The individual phases of the algorithm (intermediate results) are presented on the model of the high mountain landscape in the Tatras (the vicinity of Skalné vráta hill - the terrain comprising rocky formations along the ridge at an altitude above 1,600 meters), generalized to level 75 in Fig. 4.

A comparison of the results of different levels of generalization is shown in Fig. 5. It depicts a model of Devínska Kobyla hill, located in the western region of Bratislava, which has a vertical range of 150 to 514 meters above sea level. The model includes anthropogenic elements such as quarries, and has been generalized with a ratio of 20, 60, and 150.

Figure 4. Algorithm stages: a) initial model, b) QEMS generalization, c) skeleton using QES, d) smoothed model to create grid

The result shows that the algorithm can successfully progressively remove small features but preserve the basic shapes of the land surface. The output mesh is also sufficiently smooth without triangular artifacts from the polyhedral TIN model.

Figure 5. Generalization levels: a) initial model, b) 20, c) 60, d) 150.

V. CONCLUSION

We have created an algorithm that combines well-known algorithms for individual stages of the generalization process with a novel anisotropic division method that increases the quality of the process. The results of the algorithm are now tested and compared with the results of different generalization methods and the comparison will be presented soon.

The software is developed to run in Node.js and relies on external libraries to perform partial tasks. Once the production quality of the software is ensured, the generalization tool will be made available to the public.

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